

Annex 5.1. Illustrative examples of actions reported by businesses, including financial institutions to address biodiversity and nature's contributions to people. Note that not necessarily all actions taken by a business are reflected, outcomes are generally not reported, and that listing of a business does not entail any form of endorsement.

	Action group (high-level, covering range of actions)	Actions (types of actions included in the action group examples)	Marou (Mourou et al., 2021; Renewable Carbon, 2025)	Tony's Chocolonely (Hou Jones et al., 2024; Tony, 2024; Tony's, 2023; Tony's Chocolonely, n.d., 2022)	Patagonia (1% For the Planet, n.d.; Clayton, 2013; Patagonia, n.d.-b, n.d.-a; Patagonia works, 2020)	Natura (Natura, 2019; Natura&Co, 2023; Puppim De Oliveira et al., 2022; Simões-Coelho et al., 2023)	Ambatovy (Amabatovy, 2023)	Compagnie des Bauxites de Guinée (CBG) (Ramboll, 2022, 2024)	Anglo American (AngloAmerican, 2024)
Type of company - sector (and commodity), size, geography			Agriculture and food sector: Chocolate manufacturer Vietnam local supply chain	Agriculture and food sector: Chocolate manufacturer Medium business international supply chains	Fashion and apparel Large business	Consumer goods: Cosmetics Large business	Minerals and mining Large business	Mining	Minerals and mining
Scale of Business			SME	Greater than €150 million annual net revenue	About \$1 billion annual revenue	Net annual revenue \$4.8 billion			\$8,954 million in revenue in June 2025
Countries			Vietnam-based sourcing, processing, and manufacturing, global product sales	Netherlands, with Ghana, Ivory Coast source countries for cocoa beans, global product sales	USA, global product sales	Brazil, global product sales	Madagascar	Bauxite mining operations in Republic of Guinea, global exports (over 16 million of tonnes per year)	Headquarters in the UK, mining operations and projects across Europe, southern Africa, North and South America and Australia
Corporate	Set ambition and integrate biodiversity in corporate strategy	Define overall ambition and goals for biodiversity; Define strategy for biodiversity, ensure this is included in corporate strategy	Established with a social and environmental consciousness, and guided by six core values; One of few companies that produce chocolate at origin; Ensured fully traceable supply chain from eight regions local to its factory, and long-term commitments with farmers and fermenters	Established as a mission-based impact company; Commitment to 100% deforestation free supply chain (amongst other commitments); Guided by 5 sourcing principles, including full traceability of cocoa beans, and long-term commitments with farmers; Three-year corporate strategy, giving expression to the mission and guiding principles, developed by senior management, signed off by Board Board includes key shareholder representatives and experts	Incorporates environmentalism (nature protection) as one of its five guiding core values - preserved in its corporate charter; Changed company purpose to "We're in business to save our home planet" in 2018; Changed business model in 2022 for nature to be its main shareholder.	Launched corporate 'Commitment to Life' in 2020, stating company's goals and targets to address climate change, biodiversity loss, human rights, and community livelihood and wellbeing, with strong emphasis on the Amazon region; The environmental commitments are embedded in the Global Code of Conduct. The Commitment to Life consists of 8 goals and 29 measurable targets. E.g., - Become Net Zero, delivering 1.5°C in line with SBTi criteria, - Contribute to the protection and/or regeneration of 3 million ha of Amazon forest (from 2 million ha in 2020), - Assess and report global biodiversity impacts and dependencies by 2025,	Commits to Equator Principles and the World Bank Group's International Finance Corporation Performance Standards; Commits to voluntary compliance and monitoring programs, such as the Business and Biodiversity Offsets Program Principles; Aims to achieve no net loss in biodiversity for operational impacts.	CBG has an Environmental and Social Management Plan (ESMP), "which describes the process through which environmental, social, health and safety issues are managed by the Company." In 2021, a Biodiversity Action Plan was integrated into the ESMP. It sets out the biodiversity strategy and mitigation approach for the South Cogon operations, in line with International Finance Corporation Performance Standard 6 (PS6). BAP focuses on the areas where CBG has a level of management control over land use and biodiversity outcomes. It applies to CBG operations and impacts (direct, indirect and cumulative) in the South	Has a sustainability strategy ('Sustainable Mining Plan') with a goal to support a healthy environment by working towards carbon-neutral operations that also use less fresh water and deliver positive biodiversity outcomes. The strategy recognizes the interdependency between climate change and nature. Committed to closely align with the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework and UN's Sustainable Development Goals. The 2030 net positive impact (NPI) target is a commitment to leave the biodiversity of the areas adjacent to their operations in a better condition than when they arrived. To measure progress toward this target, Anglo American have developed a collaborative partnership

						<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 30% of key ingredients certified as regenerative by 2030, - Double the value shared with related communities (baseline 2020), - Engage 20 million people annually in the Living Amazon Cause (Causa Amazônia Viva), - Full traceability/certification of six raw materials used 		<p>Cogon concession, including mining activities, the multi-user railway, and CBG’s treatment plant and port areas.</p>	<p>with the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN).</p> <p>Another target – Reducing absolute freshwater withdrawals by 50% in water-scarce areas by 2030, relative to the 2015 baseline.</p>
	<p>Create policies, develop management systems and clarify requirements for measurement, monitoring, reporting, disclosures and assurance</p>	<p>Establish, reform policies and standards in line with strategy, incl. for procurement, remuneration, due diligence, grievances, circularity, resource use and efficiency and allocate resources to implement</p> <p>Develop biodiversity assessment and measurement protocols;</p> <p>Set more specific targets to align with overall goals in strategy;</p> <p>Develop plans and systems for environmental management, including biodiversity;</p> <p>Develop monitoring and verification systems to track progress towards targets;</p> <p>Develop plans and systems for internal and external reporting and disclosure;</p> <p>Develop a transition plan</p>	<p>Monitors with an aim to better adhere to the EUDR (EU Deforestation Regulation)</p>		<p>Wide-ranging corporate policies to implement core values at own operations and across value chain, including principles and/o policies on preferable purchasing, responsible service providers, building, , packaging and merchandising and paper procurement and use;</p> <p>Ambitious near and long-term targets set using SBTI target-setting guidance, including aiming to reach Net-Zero GHG emissions across the value chain by 2040; commitment to no more virgin petroleum fibres by the end of 2025;</p> <p>Uses Environmental Profit & Loss metric to guide product choices</p>	<p>Has established group-wide policies and action plans to address risks associated with six materials: palm, mica, alcohol, soy, cotton, and paper. These plans include specific traceability and certification requirements;</p> <p>Established the Sustainability Committee as the fifth supported committee in 2023.</p>	<p>Implements a new Health & Safety, Environment, Community and Quality Policy in 2024;</p> <p>Develops biodiversity management plan for each sites, including pre-clearing monitoring and relocation of species, with priorities given for endangered species</p>	<p>For the biodiversity action plan to be fully operational, business has committed to updating existing biodiversity monitoring programme by creating a PS6-aligned Biodiversity Monitoring and Evaluation Plan and developing a forest landscape community management programme to achieve a No Net Loss / Net Gain for identified priority biodiversity.</p> <p>Other plans - such as the Environmental Monitoring Plan, the Soil Resources Management Procedure, the Waste Management Plan, etc - contribute to biodiversity management.</p> <p>CBG is owned at 49% by the Guinean State at 51% by the Halco Mining consortium (Alcoa, Rio Tinto Group and Dadco Investments Limited), which means it must also comply with the biodiversity policies of these companies.</p>	<p>Biodiversity Management Programmes support the achievement of net positive impact. There are different steps: setting the baseline (1), identify risk (2), avoid, and minimise (3), biodiversity management plans (4), integration and execution (5) and biomonitoring (6).</p> <p>Commits to conducting biodiversity due diligence prior to any acquisitions, divestments, and site selection, and is monitored throughout the entire mining lifecycle.</p>

	<p>Transition the business, build capacity, and ensure adequate resourcing to implement policies and achieve targets</p>	<p>Implement policies, plans and processes listed above - e.g., do the assessment and measurement (iteratively) and review against targets; shift organisational structure to ensure oversight (e.g., board responsibilities and capabilities); allocate human and financial resources for implementation; attract and build appropriate capacity; communicate internally, etc.</p>	<p>Support to farmers for improving seed quality, sustainable agroforestry techniques, harvest quality consistently, and other company's goals over time (see also value chain actions below).</p>	<p>Remote-sensing analysis done of deforestation in own supply chain, with data collected from 29,236 cocoa farms since January 2014 (showed 0% of affiliated farms linked to deforestation); Adapting and improving goals (e.g., its 'impact promise' raises its goals); setting increasingly ambitious science-based targets (in this case on climate change); Adapting governance/ ownership, e.g., establishing a legal entity to secure the overall mission so that this cannot be changed; Developing internal capacity among staff, leadership.</p>	<p>Since 1985, company donates 1% of its sales to grassroots environmental organizations; Develops new recycled materials (e.g., old fishing net) and expand regenerative organic agriculture as the source of raw materials; Shifts to only renewable or recycled raw materials, (e.g., 100% organic cotton, 92% recycled nylon, 92% polyester fabric, 28% of cotton used is recycled cotton, etc.); 100% raw material responsibly sourced; Converts to renewable energy and invest in renewable energy projects; Grows the Worn Wear program, which focuses on encouraging reuse, repair and recycling to extend the life of products and reduce their environmental footprints. Continual improvement of performance against goals and targets, including through research (e.g., into less harmful materials, regenerative farming), corporate culture and investment in innovation</p>	<p>Communication and training for all associates (including the Board of Directors), management, and new employees on Global Code of Conduct; Double materiality assessment undertaken; maps nature impacts and dependencies following TNFD guidance, reports progress on several targets, such as traceability of raw materials; Follows the TNFD's LEAP methodology (Locate, Evaluate, Assess, Prepare), currently at the Locate phase; Continues to track and make progress on the company's 2030 targets; Aims to utilize the science-based Product Environmental Footprint method to measure products' environmental impact over its full life cycle.</p>	<p>Implements tailings management monitoring systems and risk assessments, aligned with the Global Industry Standard on Tailings Management; Prioritizes local procurement; Establishes monitoring system for fauna and flora diversity management, aiming for a long-term system of endangered species; Has a baseline inventory of biodiversity surrounding operation</p>	<p>Developed a roadmap for biodiversity action plan completion and implementation, with specific targets from 2021 to 2022. Biodiversity management sits with the biodiversity team, which is under the Health, Safety, Environment, Community and Quality department. The team is composed of six staff, including a Biodiversity Manager, who is in charge of the implementation of the BAP. The team collaborates with other teams, such as the Mining Team to "align mining activities with biodiversity imperatives and commitments".</p>	<p>Adopted an evidence-based roadmap for net positive impact to assess progress now and the trajectory through 2030, and, where necessary, to 2040 and beyond. To ensure each site and business is on the appropriate path towards delivering the commitment by closure, as well as contributing to nature positive outcomes. The Board's Sustainability Committee has oversight of the business's nature and biodiversity-related programmes of work and is updated at least annually on progress against those programmes and delivery of targets.</p> <p>C currently the only participant from the mining sector to be represented in the TNFD and first piloted the TNFD's LEAP approach at Kumba Iron Ore, in South Africa.</p>
	<p>Innovate in processes, products, and services</p>	<p>Redesigning products and packaging to reduce resource use/ consumption Circulating products and materials through reuse, repair, remanufacturing, and recycling - use of recycled input materials; take-back schemes to repair or remanufacture or resell; collaborative consumption models - leasing, sharing etc.</p>	<p>Provides free in-store cacao seeds to encourage consumers in urban gardening; Creates sustainable packaging from cacao husks</p>		<p>Program ('Worn Wear') to enable and encourage consumers to trade or to buy its products second-hand, extending products lifecycle; offering repair service as part of post-purchase engagement with consumers; extensive use of recycled materials in producing clothing, apparel.</p>	<p>Achieves 86.2% of recyclable, reusable and compostable packaging; Achieves minimum 95% biodegradability in products;</p>			<p>Applying circular economy principles, including a waste-management hierarchy, to improve how they assess, manage and process mineral waste.</p>

	Explore alternative business models and apply, where appropriate	Implement inclusive ownership, shareholder structure (e.g., to include non-investor stakeholders), change governance structures to expand decision-making powers to wider range of stakeholders, etc. [alternative ownership enterprises, B-Corps]	Adopts "Marou Cacao Community" - a business model that focuses on building the resilience, sustainability, and economic development of a tight-knit community of farmers, fermenters, and chocolate makers, which help protect the whole value chain against economic and environment disturbances	B-Corp and Fairtrade certified impact-led company; Has given a non-economic stake in the business to an independent legal entity, overseen by 'mission guardians' to protect the company's mission and prevent any legal changes to this (e.g., how the core mission is defined, sourcing principles, etc) Has established a foundation that receives 1% of company revenue, used for actions to support farmers beyond those that the business itself takes.	B-Corp and Fairtrade certified company; transitioned to a novel transformative ownership model in 2022: 100% of its voting stock is dedicated to the Patagonia Purpose Trust to protect the company core values and 100% of its nonvoting stock is given to the non-profit Holdfast Collective, which reinvests into the company and attains dividends dedicated to fighting the environmental crisis and protecting nature.	Certified members of the B-Corp Beauty Coalition, EcoBeauty Score Consortium and Cosmetics Europe			
Additional actions for financial institutions: Corporate level	Financing green (Fis only)	Blended finance, Green or sustainability-linked bonds, Impact investing	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Additional actions for financial institutions: Corporate level	Greening finance (FIs only)	Setting requirements for clients to take private actions (e.g., require clients to apply ESIA, mitigation hierarchy to achieve NNL/ NG, require clients to undertake value chain mapping and traceability)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Operations	Conduct Environmental and Social Impact Assessment						Conducted extensive ESIA's for all operations, including screening, scoping, impact assessment and design of mitigation measures, in line with national legislation and lender safeguards.	In 2016, commissioned consultants to undertake environmental and social monitoring of the 18.5 million tons per annum Mine Expansion Project (the 'Phase 1 - Expansion Project') in Guinea. A report was published in 2024. Appointed a consultancy as the Independent Environmental and Social Consultant in charge of auditing the implementation of the Biodiversity Action Plan.	

	Apply the mitigation hierarchy to achieve No Net Loss/ Net Gain				Committed to conducting operations to cause no unnecessary harm by continually seeking to reduce the environmental footprint and impact of own operations - including in water use and quality, energy use, greenhouse gas emissions, chemical use, toxicity, and waste - through application of principles / policies (e.g., building principles).		Committed to achieving at least no net loss, through application of the mitigation hierarchy. Implementing measures at operational sites (mine, processing plant etc) to avoid and minimise negative impacts on forests and biodiversity, restores degraded/disturbed land to native-species forest, with current effort over one-tenth of total area of operation; Offsets under "like for like" principle, with total offset area nine times larger than total area of operation. Minimizes waste production and landfill; increases waste recycling; Reduces water extraction.	The ongoing operations have a structured biodiversity team in place implementing a set of existing operational mitigation actions to manage biodiversity impacts following the principles of the mitigation hierarchy (avoid, minimise, restore, and where needed, offset impacts to biodiversity). Has a "Plateau by Plateau" framework underpinning the application of the mitigation hierarchy. This includes Land Disturbance Permits, Environmental Buffer Zones and Set-aside areas under the forest landscape community management programme. CBG mitigation actions are described in the biodiversity action plan.	To deliver net-positive impact (NPI) across all sites, the business commits to implementing the mitigation hierarchy. The Sustainable Mining Plan emphasizes that the rigorous application of the mitigation hierarchy is a requirement throughout all phases of operational life: avoiding and minimising impacts; undertaking rehabilitation and/or restoration; and offsetting, where required, any residual impacts. In 2024, all sites were progressing their biodiversity management programmes.
Value chain	Map value chain actors and ensure traceability to prioritise and inform action	Identify actors throughout the value chain (who, where, what) - to different levels of granularity (e.g., diff tiers of suppliers) Track origin of materials and products (through various methods) - all, to source, high-risk commodities, through accreditation / certification schemes, supplier control mechanisms	Nearly full mapping of value chain actors: individual farmers and fermenters; Tracking of product origins: number of trips, quantity sourced by sourcing regions, number of trees by plantations, and cultivation methods	Works directly with 11 partner cocoa cooperations in sourcing countries, representing 17,740 smallholder farmers; All farms are Global Positioning System-polygon mapped, with the information owned and used by the local producer cooperatives; 100% traceability of cocoa beans through digital platform - identifies what percent of each shipping container was supplied by which farmers.	Mapping actors in key supply chains; committed to transparency (e.g., publishing information on website) and continuously exploring best practices in material traceability and value chain transparency.	Uses certification scheme/s to map six raw materials, with current progress between 68.8% to 99.6% traceability, depending on the material			From 2025: All operations to undergo third-party audits against responsible mine certification systems

	<p>Use supplier management systems to set expectations, monitor performance and address non-compliance</p>	<p>Risk screening Use supplier management systems that operate company-wide or relate to specific commodity value chains Supplier selection based on criteria Communication of requirements to suppliers Assessment, auditing of suppliers (own, third-party...) Addressing non-compliance through engagement, suspension, exclusion</p>	<p>Supports suppliers to identify and mitigate risks as part of the company's philosophy and business model.</p>	<p>Partnership-based model with suppliers, working through company sourcing principles aimed at addressing systemic issues causing child and illegal labour, deforestation etc. along supply chains; Investment in understanding local social and environmental realities; Engagement with producers through cooperatives and professionally trained community facilitators</p>	<p>Strong chain-of-custody guidelines for suppliers; use of due diligence approaches; use of third-party certification for materials sourced, supplemented with direct auditing, where necessary.</p>	<p>Has a due diligence process: suppliers undergo assessment using its integrity and reputation protocols upon selection, and every two years thereafter; Implements Global Supplier Approval Policy in 2022 to guide ethical sourcing and supplier selection/management; conducts ESG (Environment, Social and Governance) assessment with suppliers representing 80% of the total procurement spend, aimed at improving management of the value chain; active members of industry-specific organizations such as the Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil to help increase transparency and promote ethical practices in the value chains.</p>			<p>In 2023, conducted a stakeholder-driven double materiality assessment that sought to capture the key material issues that impact society and the environment (external) and impact the business itself (internal).</p> <p>These are expected to be carried out every two to three years.</p>
	<p>Build relationships and partnerships to build capacity and drive improved performance</p>	<p>Relationship building with suppliers (e.g., through local community members) Provision of incentives (e.g., long-term contracts, premium prices) and resources (e.g., technology, financial, equipment, goods) Capacity building</p>	<p>Prices premium above commodity price and Fairtrade floor price, and increases for overtime; Monthly advances for fermenters; Supports upgrading fermentation processes and facilities through financial and technical means; Supports cacao farmers through financial incentives that rewards high-quality cacao pods production; Supports higher living and wellbeing standards for farmers, including access to water and health security; Supports regenerative agriculture and agroforestry practices, including increasing shading tree coverage, cacao variety diversification, production</p>	<p>Tony's invests in relationship building with cooperatives and member farmers, providing incentives: e.g., - Long-term sourcing agreements with 9 partner cooperatives, guaranteeing at least 5 years' sales at a higher price; Price including Fairtrade certification premium plus a living income premium. Company also invests in training and capacity building of farmer and cooperatives, including to improve crop quality, yield, use of apps to track harvests, organisational capacity, finding additional markets, etc. Transparency clause is included in collaboration agreements so that these</p>	<p>Finances energy and carbon audits for partners that focus on improving energy efficiency, implementing renewable energy off-site and on-site, and reducing coal and other carbon-intensive fuels used in material manufacturing</p>	<p>Engagement with and support for suppliers, for example quebradeiras de coco providing babassu nut oil - company commitment to purchase minimum amounts for 10-year period, paying a premium price and supporting social and business development processes - education programs, training, establishing purchasing centres and a local soap factory, improving logistical infrastructure, promoting use of fair-trade certification.</p> <p>Implements Natura Amazonia Program in 2011 to conserve millions of hectares of Amazon rainforest and support ten thousands of families living in the Pan-Amazon region;</p>	<p>Engages with SMEs to develop their capability and strengthen supply chains in Madagascar; Engages with stakeholders regarding the withdrawal strategy of the company to ensure smooth post-project transition</p>		<p>Anglo engages with suppliers through several channels, including supplier relationship management programmes, engagement events; host community procurement forums; capability development initiatives; various digital platforms; and our responsible sourcing programme.</p>

			diversification by intercropping (e.g., cacao with coconut, cashew, or fruit trees, etc.), no-tillage, using groundcover, phase-out chemical fertilizer by sustainable alternatives; Supplies farmers with high-quality, certified cacao seeds	can be shared with other buyers.		Adheres to benefit-sharing principles with IPLCs			
	Engage, educate, and incentivise downstream customers, clients and consumers	Promoting transparency and labelling to enable better choices post-purchase engagement (e.g., support / information for repair, recycle etc. to extend product lifespan) Marketing, consumer education, including on sufficiency concepts Incentivising sustainable behaviour.	Categorize products by terroir, to inform consumers of the values of local environmental qualities		Educates and raises customers and consumers awareness on product long-term uses (e.g., Worn Wear program) and environmental issues (e.g., Patagonia Action Works) and advocates for limiting consumption.	Conducts large-scale pilot of over 4,000 products from EcoBeauty Score consortium members to evaluate consumer understanding and preferences regarding the developed scoring label reflecting the product's environmental impacts			
Portfolio (actions for financial institutions)	Greening finance	Biodiversity risk/ impact management: Stewardship, engagement, voting; Diversment and exclusion	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Donations to support local community well-being and infrastructure development; Established the Social Investment Fund in 2012 with a total endowment of US\$ 25 million, dedicated to social and infrastructure projects delivering benefits to the local population	N/A	N/A

<p>System-changing/ beyond-value-chain actions</p>			<p>Marou organizes farmer seminars to inspire farmers to adopt sustainable agriculture practices which aims to improve the sector/regional sustainability as a whole</p>	<p>Tony's founded and is driving an industry initiative to encourage responsible sourcing and other actions by other companies and actors to increase impact, standing at 20 members (2023/24)</p>	<p>Patagonia initiated the Sustainable Apparel Coalition to promote social and environmental performance in the apparel industry, including an index of social and environmental performance for designers and consumers; Co-founded '1% for the Planet' in 2002 to motivate other companies to donate 1% of sales to nature conservation and environmental causes; In 2013, the company launched the \$20 Million and Change fund to support responsible start-up companies that benefit the environment; Engages in environmental stewardship and policy advocacy, in collaboration with and for the benefits of IPLCs and their nature homes; Organizes Annual Patagonia Case Competition for university students to propose solutions to lessen the company's environmental impact.</p>	<p>Together with Business for Nature and Union for Ethical BiTrade, advocates for the adoption and implementation of nature policies at both governmental and corporate levels; Supports environmental sustainability initiatives like The Earthshot Prize; Supported the following key campaigns in 2023: Fossil to Clean campaign, Zero Hour campaign, B Lab Stakeholder Governance campaigns (UK Better Business Act, EU Interdependence Coalition, Global B Movement Builders Stakeholder Governance), signed the letter backing the International Sustainability Standards Board, and Natura & Co team members joined Queue for Climate and Nature; To create science-based targets, Natura network with partners such as the Union for Ethical BioTrade, Science Based Targets Network, and a global coalition comprising Business for Nature, the World Economic Forum, and the World Business Council for Sustainable Development; Advocates the need for harmonizing the rules on benefit sharing and access to Amazonian biodiversity with governments and civil society at the level of Latin America</p>	<p>Engages with NGOs on various recycling projects; Enhances educational opportunities for children in local communities; The Livelihoods Development program provides resources and knowledge strategically designed to fortify food security, diversify, and increase income sources, cultivate self-reliance, and support sustainable long-term development of local communities; Implements comprehensive awareness and prevention programs focused on HIV/AIDS and STIs</p>		
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Table 5.3. Illustrative examples of actions reported by businesses, including financial institutions to address biodiversity and nature’s contributions to people. Note that not necessarily all actions taken by a business are reflected, outcomes are generally not reported, and that listing of a business does not entail any form of endorsement.

	Action group (high-level, covering range of actions)	Actions (types of actions included in the action group)	Holcim (Holcim, 2022, 2023)	Iberdrola (Iberdrola, 2024b, 2024a, 2025b, 2025a; WBCSD, 2023)	UPM Kymmene (Ruosteenoja et al., 2024; UPM, n.d., 2024, 2025)	Sogrape (Sogrape, n.d., 2023, 2024)	Olam Group (Olam, 2024, 2025)	Hermes (Hermès, 2023, 2024b, 2024a, 2025)	Rabobank (Rabobank, 2024b, 2024a)	Aviva (Aviva, 2021, 2024)
Type of company - sector (and commodity), size, geography			Cement and concrete Large	Renewable energy Large	Forest products Large	Agriculture and food sector Medium? (<1,200 employees)	Agriculture and food sector Large	Fashion and apparel Large	Cooperative Bank focused on food and agriculture sector	General insurer and a leading life and pensions provider
Scale of Business				Net profit \$5.6 billions		€16 million net profit in 2024	\$56,157.1million in revenue in 2024	€15,170 million in revenue in 2024		
Countries			Switzerland, global product sales	Multinational corporation	Finland, global operation	Portuguese-owned, with production across Portugal, Spain, Argentina, Chile, and New Zealand and global product sales	Singapore, with 60+ countries of operation	France, with global product sales	Netherlands with international operations	Core markets including UK, Ireland, Canada
Corporate	Set ambition and integrate biodiversity in corporate strategy	Define overall ambition and goals for biodiversity; Define strategy for biodiversity, ensure this is included in corporate strategy	Launched nature strategy in 2021, focusing on restoring and preserving biodiversity and freshwater ecosystems; commits not to open new sites or explorations within protected areas declared under World Heritage, International Union for the Conservation of Nature I and III	Integrated Governance and Sustainability System as a core corporate mission in 2016; Updated the Strategic Vision in 2024, focusing on rising opportunities from sustainable energy demand, reflected in commitments and reinforced investment strategy with €41 billion over 2024-2026 on promoting economy’s electrification and anticipating new sources of electricity demand; Implemented a Biodiversity Policy in 2007 and revised in 2022 with commitment to have a net positive impact on biodiversity by 2030; Establishes a roadmap aimed at achieving carbon neutrality for Scopes 1 and 2 by 2030 and net zero emissions for all scopes, including Scope 3, by 2040 90% of the company's long-term investment	Corporate and business strategy plans are updated on an annual basis and built on continuous monitoring of trends and indicators; Committed to highest standards in sustainable forest management and zero deforestation; Committed to net positive impact on forest biodiversity.	Launched its first Nature and Biodiversity Strategy in 2024, establishing a structured plan to reduce environmental impact and strengthen ecosystem resilience. This strategy aligns with its Global Sustainability Programme, titled «Seed the Future». Recognized through the "It's Now for Nature" campaign, promoted by Business4Nature, which highlighted Sogrape as a reference case in sustainability in the wine sector. Sogrape started conducting Sustainability Reports in 2022 and these are updated on an annual basis to monitor progress against targets.	Adopted a Sustainability Framework to achieve the company's purpose to "Re-imagine Global Agriculture and Food Systems". The SF defines three key outcomes: • prosperous farmers and food systems; • thriving communities; and • regeneration of the living world There are ten Priority Areas in the Sustainability Framework, five falling into the third outcome "regeneration of the living world": climate action, healthy ecosystems, healthy soils, water and reduced waste. Each of these Priority Areas have a set of principles that commit to protect ecosystems, biodiversity and watersheds in the locations where it operates. E.g., For	Formalised Biodiversity Strategy in 2018 and updated in 2020 around four structuring elements: train, collaborate, assess, and act. It is in line with the Sustainable Development Strategic Framework defined by the House in 2015 and updated in 2020. Through this strategy, business defines its ambition—a strong commitment to protecting biodiversity and ecosystems across three levels: within its direct sphere of responsibility, its extended sphere of influence, and through voluntary actions beyond its economic interests. Recognizes and aligns its strategy with the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, particularly Target 15,	Launched Nature Vision and Approach titled 'Value nature – Back to planetary boundaries' in 2024 with ultimate vision to 'integrate nature in our way of working by 2030 and live in harmony with nature by 2050' in alignment with the vision and targets of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework.	Signed the Finance for Biodiversity Pledge in 2021 and joined the Terra Carta Initiative. As part of its commitments under the Finance for Biodiversity Pledge, the business aims to play its part in reversing the loss of nature by 2030. Signed the Financial Sector Commitment Letter on Eliminating Commodity-Driven Deforestation. Through this commitment, the business pledged to use its best efforts—via engagement and stewardship—to eliminate deforestation linked to forest-risk agricultural commodities within its investment portfolio and financing activities by 2025.

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				plan is aligned with the green investment criteria included in the European Union's Taxonomy;			<p>healthy soils, Olam commits to minimise soil disturbance, keep soil covered and living roots in the soil, favour organic input sources, etc.</p> <p>In 2024, Olam Food Ingredients, a part of Olam Group, has launched its own sustainability strategy "Choices for Change" with 2030 targets, including bringing 2 million hectares of land under regenerative farming practices, becoming forest positive across the business and creating 20 living landscapes partnerships to regenerate nature.</p>	<p>as well as the French National Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 (SNB). Also aligns its biodiversity actions with major international frameworks such as Act4Nature International (since 2018), Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures (TNFD) and SBTN to support the global goals defined by the Kunming-Montreal Framework.</p> <p>Sustainable Development Department leads the biodiversity strategy, which is implemented across operational departments. In the Sustainable Development Department sit two members of the Executive Committee, one responsible for the upstream division (supply chains and manufacturing sites) and the other for organisational development.</p>		
	Create policies, develop management systems, and clarify requirements for measurement, monitoring, reporting, disclosures and assurance	Establish, reform policies and standards in line with strategy, incl. for procurement, remuneration, due diligence, grievance, circularity, resource use and efficiency and allocate resources to implement Develop biodiversity assessment and measurement protocols; Set more specific targets to align with overall goals in strategy;	Commitments to water include: Freshwater use reduction, High water quality standard, and Freshwater replenishment. Commitments to biodiversity include: Progressive and transformative rehabilitation, Rigorous biodiversity measurement and monitoring, Increasing circularity, Reforestation, Multi-stakeholder landscape	Focuses investments on regions with clear and stable regulatory frameworks; Commits to no net deforestation throughout operation and supply chain by 2025; 100% of installations to have biodiversity action plan by 2030; Follows mitigation and conservation hierarchy; Promotes the conservation and planting of 20 million	Has set targets and KPIs on responsible sourcing, sustainable forest use, enhancing biodiversity, energy efficiency, waste reduction and recycling, and responsible water use; Committed to becoming a net carbon sink (more growth than harvest); Adopted a renewed Sustainability Policy Statement in 2025, which covers risks, opportunities, impacts, and	As part of its Global Sustainability Program, has established strategic priorities across three pillars, comprising nine commitments and eleven flagship targets. Each target is accompanied by a Key Performance Indicator, all slated to be achieved by 2027. The three pillars of Seed the Future are: 1. Pave the way to a healthier planet: Sustain our planet for	Olam Food Ingredients set a regenerative agriculture action plan as well as a forest-positive action plan, with goals and specific actions to achieve the 2030 targets. Along with the Sustainability Framework, business published a Supplementary Sustainability Disclosures report, which contains	Biodiversity Strategy assesses the impacts of its activities on biodiversity and the risks related to biodiversity loss on its business model, particularly on its supply chains. Has developed a series of policies, including an environmental policy (2025), a Vigilance Plan, a Sustainable Purchasing Policy and Forest Policy - all are part of a set of key	As a part of broader Sustainability Policy Framework, has defined Biodiversity Policy, alongside specific sector policies for sectors where investment poses highest biodiversity risk. Biodiversity Policy includes commitments to: Avoid contributing to biodiversity loss; Support clients in preserving biodiversity and ecosystem services;	A Biodiversity Policy was put in place with the following goals: Target-setting: Establish and disclose measurable targets to increase positive contributions and reduce negative impacts on biodiversity. Underwriting alignment: Review risk appetite and underwriting boundaries to focus

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		<p>Develop plans and systems for environmental management, including biodiversity; Develop monitoring and verification systems to track progress towards targets; Develop plans and systems for internal and external reporting and disclosure; Develop a transition plan</p>	<p>approach, and Manage supply chain; Committed to 2030 circularity economy targets: recycle 20 million tons of construction demolition materials per annum, Increase recycled content in cement to 30%, recycle 70 million tons of waste and byproducts for alternative energy and raw materials</p>	<p>trees by 2030 (baseline 0 in 2020)</p>	<p>dependencies evaluation using double materiality assessment, sustainability due diligence, target-setting and monitoring progress, incorporating biodiversity among key topics; Reporting complying with CSRD and EUDR, and following reporting standards of GRI and EMAS</p>	<p>future generations. 2. Safeguard our legacy on its journey into the future: Ensure that wine and its culture can be experienced by generations to come. 3. Inspire happier and more responsible lives: Be a catalyst of positive change in society, among our people and with our consumers.</p> <p>Examples of targets: - By 2027 Sogrape will advance circular and nature-based solutions across all businesses with at least five projects in each Business Unit and have 60 circular economy and nature projects. - By 2027 Sogrape will have 100% of its strategic suppliers embrace sustainable practices.</p>	<p>sustainability data aligned with GRI standards.</p>	<p>documents related to the Corporate Social Responsibility of Hermès.</p>	<p>Promote sustainable and nature-inclusive farming practices; and collaborate with stakeholders to develop biodiversity solutions; Has put in place an 'exclusion list' precludes financing of: Deforestation or conversion of high conservation value areas;</p> <p>Introduction of non-native species into undisturbed ecosystems;</p> <p>Illegal or unauthorized trade in threatened wildlife or products regulated by CITES or the IUCN Red List; 'Exclusion list' also precludes business with clients that used illegal fires for land clearing in the past five years; operate in nationally or internationally protected areas; or harm or contribute to the decline of endangered species.</p>	<p>on areas where Aviva can drive the greatest change.</p> <p>Procurement integration: Incorporate biodiversity considerations into procurement decisions.</p> <p>Safeguards and screening: Strengthen safeguards and screening practices for high-impact sectors across investment and underwriting activities.</p> <p>World Heritage protection: Develop robust policies to safeguard World Heritage Sites, drawing on the joint guidance from WWF, UNEP FI, PSI, and UNESCO.</p> <p>Transparency: Report annually on progress, including both positive and negative contributions to global biodiversity goals through financing and investment activities.</p>

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	Transition the business, build capacity, and ensure adequate resourcing to implement policies and achieve targets	Implement policies, plans and processes listed above - e.g., do the assessment and measurement (iteratively) and review against targets; shift organisational structure to ensure oversight (e.g., board responsibilities and capabilities); allocate human and financial resources for implementation; attract and build appropriate capacity; communicate internally, etc.	<p>Annual assessments of water and biodiversity based on Holcim's Nature Policy conducted across all sites, and expected from suppliers;</p> <p>Has a decarbonization action plan for each step of the production process, including value chain;</p> <p>In 2024, Holcim assessed 100% of its biodiversity baseline in all active and non-active quarries using the Biodiversity Indicator and Reporting System.</p> <p>Enters a global strategic partnership with the International Union for the Conservation of Nature - IUCN will validate its biodiversity baseline, while identifying ways for it to improve biodiversity levels across its operations by 2030;</p> <p>Member of the TNFD, and piloting the Science-Based Target for Nature framework pilot;</p>	<p>Has a global Environmental Management System that integrates the principle of pollution prevention in all of its processes and activities;</p> <p>Establishes a new biodiversity accounting framework to quantify impacts on ecosystems and species arising from the construction, operation, and decommissioning of company's facilities;</p> <p>Improve impact measurements in the value chain by calculating Corporate Environmental Footprint;</p> <p>Collaborates with stakeholders and takes part in research to understand the behaviour of species and habitats in the countries where it operates;</p> <p>Identifies risks and opportunities using TNFD's LEAP;</p> <p>Discloses Corporate Environmental Footprint, verified by external and independent verification;</p> <p>Participates in TNFD pilot;</p> <p>Aligns biodiversity goal with SBTN guidance;</p>	<p>Fully maps all pulp and paper mills on the Water Stress Index maps since 2011, and conducted water risk analysis based on the WWF’s Water Risk Filter.</p> <p>Corporate and business strategy plans are updated on an annual basis and built on continuous monitoring of trends and indicators;</p> <p>Innovates sustainable products and packaging, guided by the company's sustainable design concept;</p> <p>Participating in SBTN pilot;</p> <p>Participating in eDNA monitoring pilot project;</p> <p>Works with research partners to monitor and improve soil carbon, habitat health, and better understand carbon cycle of tree species in changing climate.</p>	<p>Has outlined and undertaken a series of actions to conserve biodiversity. It conducts research and formulation of Ecosystem Management and Agroecology Plans. It assessed viticulture's effects on biodiversity and soil, followed by the adoption of mitigation strategies for any adverse impacts and implementation of intervention plans along with improvement measures.</p> <p>E.g., Alternative measures to the use of phytosanitary products.</p> <p>In 2023, Sogrape achieved a significant milestone by obtaining the National Reference for Sustainability Certification in the Wine Sector, in all the Portuguese regions where it produces wine.</p>	<p>In 2021, agreed a shared roadmap -the Agriculture Sector Roadmap - to accelerate actions to halt commodity-linked deforestation supply chains, including soy and palm, consistent with a 1.5C pathway.</p> <p>Since 2019, Olam has followed the recommendations of the Financial Stability Board’s Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures (TCFD). It will disclose its respective nature-related dependencies, impacts, risks, and opportunities (DIROs) in line with TNFD recommendations from FY2025.</p> <p>Since 2020, it is included in the FTSE4Good Index Series.</p>	<p>Since 2023, it uses the Science Based Targets for Nature (SBTN) method. To date, Hermès has completed the initial steps of the approach: step 1 'assessing the pressures exerted by the company on biodiversity and step 2 'Interpreting and prioritizing sites, priority sectors, and work to be carried out'. The Group has not started step 3 'measuring, setting and disclosing'.</p> <p>Has also developed a “Nature Master Plan” to structure both existing and new actions aimed at reducing the impact of its sites on key biodiversity pressures.</p> <p>Biodiversity strategy was reviewed in 2020, setting new targets for 2026. This strategy has been validated by a panel of experts and is based on two recognized scientific approaches: SBTN – Science Based Targets for Nature and the Global Biodiversity Score.</p> <p>In 2024, Hermès renewed its partnership with Act4Nature International.</p>	<p>Has outlined and undertaken a series of actions and measurement initiatives to integrate nature into its operations and achieve its sustainability goals; it aimed to include nature within the scope of its double materiality analysis by the end of 2024; by the same deadline, it conducted a top-down assessment of nature impacts for the significant majority of its nature-material portfolio; it gathered collateral polygon data for the majority of its rural clients; for Dutch dairy clients, sustainability scores were based on data from the Biodiversity Monitor and the Open Soil Index by the end of 2025; by the end of 2024, the institution implemented a clear nature governance framework and assigned senior management accountability; it developed a nature vision and integrated it into the broader sustainability strategy; nature-related policies were further developed and updated by the end of 2025; nature was further integrated into business strategies and plans for prioritized sectors and regions by the end of 2024; the institution worked toward setting impact targets on material nature topics in these prioritized sectors and regions by</p>	<p>Now drawing on the TPT disclosure framework, launched in October 2023, to inform the development of its second transition plan.</p>

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									the end of 2025; nature-sensitive portfolios were increasingly incorporated into its risk management approach; it allocated EUR 3 billion to support the sustainability transition of Dutch food and agriculture clients between 2023 and 2030; it conducted client transition dialogues with Dutch food and agriculture clients by the end of 2024.	
	Innovate in processes, products, and services	Redesigning products and packaging to reduce resource use/ consumption Circulating products and materials through reuse, repair, remanufacturing, and recycling - use of recycled input materials; take-back schemes to repair or remanufacture or resell; collaborative consumption models - leasing, sharing etc.				Has invested in innovative products and packaging to enhance sustainability and efficiency. Prioritises using paper with higher recycling content and reusing and recycling of packaging, especially for distribution. Some results: 1. 100% of cardboard boxes made from recycled paper at LAN in Spain. 2. Percentage of shipping cartons recycled: - 100% in Portugal - 61% at Viña Los Boldos 3. Barrels are made from sustainable source wood. Sogrape Portugal uses materials derived from wood sourced from sustainably managed forests, with FSC® certification. The FSC label certifies		One of the guiding principles of the environmental policy is "to reuse materials and objects, reduce waste production, and recover waste as much as possible". The Group circular economy strategy focuses on optimizing material and consumable use, circular manufacturing, waste management within operations, and end-of-life management of products. The 2024 Vigilance Plan reported that 58% of all waste is recovered (recycling, reuse, energy recovery). In the coming years, several objectives related to circular economy and waste management have been set: • Achieve 100% elimination of unnecessary single-use plastics by 2030. • Establish a recycling pathway for all unsold products by 2030.		

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						that the packaging and paper are made from responsibly sourced wood fibre.		• Define site-specific waste reduction targets based on circular economy principles and grounded in science.		
	Explore alternative business models and apply, where appropriate	Implement inclusive ownership, shareholder structure (e.g., to include non-investor stakeholders), change governance structures to expand decision-making powers to wider range of stakeholders, etc. [alternative ownership enterprises, B-Corps]		Shifted business model in 2001, by identifying new opportunities for investing in sustainable energy following the Kyoto Protocol and EU regulations		N/A	N/A	N/A		
Additional actions for financial institutions: Corporate level	Financing green (Fis only)	Blended finance, Green or sustainability-linked bonds, Impact investing	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Collects supporting information for all clients, from upstream to downstream, to demonstrate that they have established—and are working to improve—sustainable production and sourcing practices, including chain of custody controls, particularly through Round Table on Responsible Soy Association (RTRS) certification or the production or sourcing of RTRS-certified soy upstream clients; For upstream clients, supporting information is collected to demonstrate that they: maintain sustainable business practices, particularly in the	Aviva Investors launched the Natural Capital Transition Global Equity Fund in 2021 to support the transition to a nature-positive economy while delivering long-term client returns. The fund targets companies driving solutions or leading their sectors on sustainable land, oceans, the circular economy, and climate change, with every holding engaged on biodiversity over three years and divested if progress is lacking. Part of the management fee funds ecosystem restoration, and Aviva engages policymakers to tackle systemic drivers of biodiversity loss.

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									<p>responsible use of land and water, soil management, and the application of agrochemicals;</p> <p>conduct social and environmental i+Q11+Q10ir current sourcing practices and have plans to increase the sourcing of sustainably produced soy.</p>	<p>In 2022, Aviva introduced the Natural Capital Transition Engagement Programme (NCEP), engaging 43 companies to assess impacts, set time-bound targets, and address key sector risks. Progress is reviewed annually, with underperformers escalated through engagement, voting, and potential divestment. -In Canada, Aviva funds WWF-Canada's Nature and Climate Grant Program, supporting local groups and Indigenous organisations in restoring degraded lands and shorelines to improve habitats and capture carbon.</p>
Additional actions for financial institutions: Corporate level	Greening finance (FIs only)	Setting requirements for clients to take private actions (e.g., require clients to apply ESIA, mitigation hierarchy to achieve NNL/ NG, require clients to undertake value chain mapping and traceability)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	<p>Collects supporting information for all clients, from upstream to downstream, to demonstrate that they have established—and are working to improve—sustainable production and sourcing practices, including chain of custody controls, particularly through Round Table on Responsible Soy Association (RTRS) certification or the production or sourcing of RTRS-certified soy. Upstream Clients; For upstream clients, supporting information is collected to demonstrate that they:</p>	<p>Each January, business sends a letter to the chairs of companies it invests in—and some it does not—to outline stewardship priorities. In 2022, Aviva wrote to over 1,600 global companies urging them to develop biodiversity action plans that assess impacts and dependencies, set interim and comprehensive SBTN-aligned targets, and publicly report progress. -Biodiversity was also made an annual sovereign engagement priority in 2022. Aviva's CEO wrote to finance ministers and central</p>

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									<p>maintain sustainable business practices, particularly in the responsible use of land and water, soil management, and the application of agrochemicals;</p> <p>conduct social and environmental impact assessments for new developments and incorporate the findings into their operational planning and management.</p> <p>Mid- and Downstream Companies For mid- and downstream companies, supporting information is collected to show that they:</p> <p>have purchasing policies that address sustainability concerns related to soy production;</p> <p>are transparent about their current sourcing practices and have plans to increase the sourcing of sustainably produced soy.</p>	<p>bank governors from over 30 countries, calling for support of the post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework and for central banks to assess financial system dependencies on nature. Sovereign responses welcomed this focus and shared updates on policy progress.</p>
Operations	Conduct Environmental and Social Impact Assessment		Conducts ESG assessment	Conducts ESIA's to avoid building new infrastructure projects in areas protected due to their ecological, biological, cultural and/or scenic value, or in areas classified as high biodiversity value, when the value of these areas would be affected, unless there are no viable alternatives. Where significant impacts have been identified,	Conducts Environmental and Social Impact Assessment	Sogrape Portugal conducted extensive biodiversity studies across its estates in 2021 and 2022 with the goal of enhancing vineyard conditions, conserving biodiversity, and contributing to ecosystem preservation. The findings and proposed actions are being implemented to	Followed the TNFD's Locate, Evaluate, Assess and Prepare (LEAP) approach, and additional sector guidance, for the identification and assessment of nature-related issues. The scope of the assessment included 169 direct operations and upstream sourcing locations for 10 commodities: wood, rubber, cotton,	Measures its biodiversity footprint according to the five pressures of IPBES (habitat degradation, pollution, climate change, resource exploitation, and invasive species and others).		

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				the project is modified using bestavailable techniques and measures identified as being necessary to correct and minimise them.		initiate a transition to agroecology and nature-positive viticulture.	rice, wheat, soy, maize, palm oil, coffee and nuts (almonds).			
	Apply the mitigation hierarchy to achieve No Net Loss/ Net Gain		The mitigation hierarchy is embedded within company's Quarry Rehabilitation and Biodiversity Directive; Substituting waste materials and by products from other industries as raw materials in the production process; Reduces clinker carbon footprint by recycling and replacing with alternatives; Innovates large-scale carbon capture, utilization and storage solutions, as well as energy efficiency and alternative fuels; Innovative technology to recycle construction demolition materials into construction products; Restore quarries into biodiverse wetland habitat; Provides innovative bio-active concrete solutions to help rehabilitate damaged coastal ecosystems	The mitigation hierarchy is the guiding principle and embedded in the Biodiversity Plan; Implements various research, monitoring, improvement, and conservation projects to reduce impacts and improve the conservation of species and ecosystems in operating regions, including coral reefs, migratory birds, Lear's Macaw, native plants, bats, etc.; Other actions include offsetting and restoration of degraded land and ecosystems from various programs Sets aside €40 million over to protect plant life between 2018 and 2019 in Spain; Invests around 200 million euros to adapt and correct 234,000 electrical supports in order to minimise the impact of overhead lines on birdlife in Spain	All company-owned forests and plantations are certified (FSC and PEFC) or in the process of being certified if the site is new; Restoring mixed forest by collaborating and building relationships with indigenous communities; Launched habitat programme for company owned forests for 2024–2030 to enhance forest biodiversity and habitat resilience.	Follows the mitigation hierarchy, particularly focusing on avoidance, minimize, and restoration. Has implemented several actions to protect and restore biodiversity. For example, preventing the introduction of invasive species, adaptation to manage proliferation of weeds, ecological structure recovery and creation of habitats for predatory species, vineyard blocks designed according to detailed soil surveys, tree planting, responsible farming practices, etc.				Biodiversity was also made an annual sovereign engagement priority in 2022. Aviva's CEO wrote to finance ministers and central bank governors from over 30 countries, calling for support of the post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework and for central banks to assess financial system dependencies on nature. Sovereign responses welcomed this focus and shared updates on policy progress.

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Value chain	Map value chain actors and ensure traceability to prioritise and inform action	Identify actors throughout the value chain (who, where, what) - to different levels of granularity (e.g., diff tiers of suppliers) Track origin of materials and products (through various methods) - all, to source, high-risk commodities, through accreditation / certification schemes, supplier control mechanisms	Conducts Double Materiality Assessment, including the process steps, value chain mapping, stakeholder mapping, an analysis of the qualitative and quantitative results, and the validation steps			Recognises the importance of sustainable practices in responsible procurement within its supply chain and the development of partnerships with suppliers dedicated to sustainability. Examples: 1. Policies and procedures implemented by the respective departments, exemplified by the Purchase Norm and Policy. 2. The Sustainability Policy was implemented at Liberty Wines in 2023.	Uses the Integrated Biodiversity Assessment Tool (IBAT) to screen for biodiversity risks within their supply chains and operations. Task Force for Nature-related Financial Disclosures.	Taking steps to assess impacts on biodiversity throughout its value chain. Value chain mapping and the construction of an impact analysis matrix make it possible to monitor and manage these impacts. By 2026, it will measure the biodiversity footprint of its supply chains (leather, silk, cashmere, wood, cotton) using the Global Biodiversity Score (GBS) approach.		
	Use supplier management systems to set expectations, monitor performance and address non-compliance	Risk screening Use supplier management systems that operate company-wide or relate to specific commodity value chains Supplier selection based on criteria Communication of requirements to suppliers Assessment, auditing of suppliers (own, third-party...) Addressing non-compliance through engagement, suspension, exclusion	Uses Climate and Nature Risks and Opportunities Assessment to identify impacts, risks, and opportunities; Decarbonizes value chain by using lower carbon footprint alternatives for fuels and energy, downstream transportation, purchased clinker and cement, and other products and services;	A preliminary qualitative analysis of risks was conducted for the whole value chain; Its suppliers are required to have due diligence policies and systems in place to ensure their services are compliant	Has a comprehensive compliance system embedded in corporate strategy; Assessed and reported nature-related dependencies, impacts, risks, and opportunities according to the TNFD recommendations in 2024		Conducted biodiversity risk assessments of 88 primary (Tier 1) and secondary (Tier 2) sites (68 Olam Agri, 20 OGH) using the Integrated Biodiversity Assessment Tool (IBAT-Pro) for multi-site reporting. Assessment, auditing of suppliers: Olam works with third parties that assess and report the company's progress to achieve sustainable supply chains.	Risk assessment: Hermès pledges in its 'Vigilance Plan' that "impacts of materials are carefully studied, in particular using supply chain analyses, product life cycle analyses and biodiversity studies". Communication of requirements: Supply chain and CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility) briefs are provided to partners. Assessment, auditing of suppliers: To ensure that these materials are sourced in a way that preserves natural ecosystems and biodiversity, Hermès also conducts regular audits and evaluations of its suppliers to identify environmental (particularly risks		Aviva carried out a deforestation risk assessment in 2022 across its financial portfolios, underwriting, and operations, with a focus on commodity-driven deforestation. Key Findings: Corporate holdings: Around 26% show exposure to deforestation; over half are financial institutions, and most exposed companies are weak or medium in managing risk. Sovereign debt: Exposure to high tree-cover loss countries is small (e.g., Brazil ~0.3% of holdings; total commodity-linked deforestation exposure ~1.2%). Real assets: Exposure to commodity-driven

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								related to deforestation and biodiversity loss), social and ethical risks.		deforestation is negligible or zero
	Build relationships and partnerships to build capacity and drive improved performance	Relationship building with suppliers (e.g., through local community members) Provision of incentives (e.g., long-term contracts, premium prices) and resources (e.g., technology, financial, equipment, goods) Capacity building	Builds capacity throughout the value chain through innovative technology, emission efficiency, knowledge sharing, and finance			Target 2027: Sogrape works with 100% of its strategic farmers to help them become more economically and environmentally sustainable	Olam ofi provides training programs (465,000 farmers trained in good agricultural practices), resources (credit, fertilizer inputs, tools, equipment), social and economic support, etc.	The biodiversity strategy is communicated and explained to suppliers, subcontractors and other stakeholders involved in its implementation via appropriate briefs and communications to ensure a common understanding and ownership of the objectives and actions.		
	Engage, educate, and incentivise downstream customers, clients and consumers	Promoting transparency and labelling to enable better choices post-purchase engagement (e.g., support / information for repair, recycle etc. to extend product lifespan) Marketing, consumer education, including on sufficiency concepts Incentivising sustainable behaviour.				Example: Sogrape includes nature and biodiversity in its wine production and marketing, fostering a connection between the winery and consumers. This approach is intended to encourage consumers to act as guardians of nature.	Sustainability insights platform for agricultural supply chains, at Source provides customers with a single view across their supply chain sustainability parameters, as well as insights into how to influence these elements for the better.	Through its Foundation, launched the third edition of Manuterra in 2023, an educational programme dedicated to introducing young generations to permaculture during school hours. The 12 two-hour immersive sessions encourage children to foster a deeper connection with nature and to highlight the major challenges in protecting and preserving it. For the 2024-2025 school year, Manuterra will operate in 11 school boards.		

	Action group (high-level, covering range of actions)	Actions (types of actions included in the action group)	Holcim (Holcim, 2022, 2023)	Iberdrola (Iberdrola, 2024b, 2024a, 2025b, 2025a; WBCSD, 2023)	UPM Kymmene (Ruosteenoja et al., 2024; UPM, n.d., 2024, 2025)	Sogrape (Sogrape, n.d., 2023, 2024)	Olam Group (Olam, 2024, 2025)	Hermès (Hermès, 2023, 2024b, 2024a, 2025)	Rabobank (Rabobank, 2024b, 2024a)	Aviva (Aviva, 2021, 2024)
Portfolio (actions for financial institutions)	Greening finance	Biodiversity risk/ impact management: Stewardship, engagement, voting; Divestment and exclusion		N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A		<p>Aviva's default approach is to engage with companies, encouraging and supporting them to address biodiversity impacts and dependencies while managing associated risks. Divestment is not the preferred option; however, retaining it as a possibility gives engagement greater leverage.</p> <p>The company already applies baseline investment and underwriting exclusions for Arctic drilling and oil sands. In addition, Aviva Investors has embedded several nature-related commitments into its voting policy, such as urging companies to abstain from operating in, or sourcing materials from, protected areas, key biodiversity areas, or other environmentally sensitive zones.</p> <p>In its voting policy, Aviva has committed to the following:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) It will vote in favour of proposals that call on companies to abstain from operating in, or sourcing materials from, protected areas, key biodiversity areas, or other environmentally sensitive zones. 2) It will vote against targeted management resolutions at the

	Action group (high-level, covering range of actions)	Actions (types of actions included in the action group)	Holcim (Holcim, 2022, 2023)	Iberdrola (Iberdrola, 2024b, 2024a, 2025b, 2025a; WBCSD, 2023)	UPM Kymmene (Ruosteenoja et al., 2024; UPM, n.d., 2024, 2025)	Sogrape (Sogrape, n.d., 2023, 2024)	Olam Group (Olam, 2024, 2025)	Hermès (Hermès, 2023, 2024b, 2024a, 2025)	Rabobank (Rabobank, 2024b, 2024a)	Aviva (Aviva, 2021, 2024)
										<p>worst-performing forest-risk commodity companies listed in the Global Canopy Forest 500 ranking.</p> <p>3) It will support shareholder resolutions that ask management to assess, report on, and reduce key impacts and dependencies on nature in high-impact sectors. - Voted against management at 75 companies due to their poor deforestation policies. -Voted in favour of 19 biodiversity-related shareholder resolutions.</p>
System-changing/ beyond-value-chain actions			<p>Advocates for the establishment of mandatory rehabilitation requirements in public policy; Partners with academia for research and innovation; Creates new platforms to share knowledge and promote best practices in sustainable construction</p> <p>Has a foundation - Holcim Foundation for Sustainable Construction - to support and connect innovators in the built environment.</p>	<p>Supports action for biodiversity and nature in international negotiation processes such as the agreements of the Biodiversity Conventions of the Parties, the UN Oceans Conferences, implementation of national and supranational Biodiversity Strategies.</p> <p>Collaborates with private sector representative bodies such as Business for Nature, World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD), International Chamber of Commerce (ICC),</p>	<p>Linked a EUR 750 million revolving credit facility with a margin tied to long-term biodiversity and climate targets</p>	<p>Commits to SDGs, has also joined the United Nations Global Compact programme and subscribed to the COP16 business declaration, reinforcing the commitment to biodiversity protection and sustainability.</p> <p>Actively contributes to six of the UN Sustainability Goals (SDGs), among which SDG 12 'Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns' and SDG 13 'Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts'.</p>	<p>Signatory of the 'Business Ambition for 1.5 C' commitment with approved targets since 2019.</p> <p>At COP27, Olam joined with 14 global agri-commodity companies in the Agriculture Sector Roadmap to 1.5°C, aiming to reduce emissions from land-use change consistent with a 1.5°C pathway.</p> <p>Committed to disclose its respective nature-related dependencies, impacts, risks and opportunities (DIROs) in line with Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures (TNFD)</p>	<p>Signed a partnership agreement with WWF France, launched in 2016 and renewed in 2020 and again in 2023 for three years. Since 2023, Is a member of the Laboratoire Capital Naturel ('Lab') - founded by WWF France and the Chair of Ecological Accounting led by AgroParisTech Foundation - and supports the development of strong sustainability frameworks such as Science-Based Targets Network (SBTN). It joined the SBTN Corporate Engagement Program in 2023. Also collaborates with CDC Biodiversité</p>	<p>Signed the Finance for Biodiversity Pledge in 2020. Since then, it has actively participated in leading initiatives such as the Partnership for Biodiversity Accounting Financials (PBAF) and the Biodiversity Working Group at the Dutch Central Bank (DNB). In 2021, it joined the Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures (TNFD) as a Taskforce member from its inception.</p>	<p>At the global level, Aviva has worked closely with its strategic partner, WWF, to advance an ambitious outcome at the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) COP15 in Montreal in 2022.</p>

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				<p>World Economic Forum (WEF), UN Global Compact, etc., as well as with the scientific community, such as the Intergovernmental Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES).</p> <p>Contributes to the transformation of the energy sector and society as a whole to achieve an economic and energy model in harmony with nature and mankind.</p>		<p>Initiatives: PORVID - Portuguese Association for Grapevine Diversity was cofounded in 2009 by Sogrape and various associations, institutions, and companies in the wine sector. The primary objective of this association is to preserve Portugal's native grapevines, safeguarding their varieties and clones across different regions of the country.</p>	<p>recommendations from FY2025.</p> <p>Support global and industry-wide initiatives to advance positive and sustainable change, as well as collaborating with multiple organisations</p>	<p>through its participation in the B4B+ Club’s (Business for Positive Biodiversity Club) working groups on value chains and biodiversity credits/certificates, contributing to the ongoing dialogue on biodiversity footprint methodologies.</p> <p>Demonstrates further commitment to promoting biodiversity through its contributions to the Act4Nature initiative – of which it is a signatory –, its investment in the Livelihoods funds, and the actions it takes within the framework of its Foundation - Foundation d’entreprise Hermès (created in 2008). One of its core programmes 'Biodiversity and Ecosystems' has launched different initiatives, such as working since 2021 with the Federation of Catalan Nature Reserves to ensure the preservation the Massane beech forest, located in the Pyrénées-Orientales department.</p>		

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Methodological assessment of the impact and dependence of business on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people.
Chapter 5. Businesses as key actors in transformative change: options for action

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